

ON THERMAL STUDIES OF SiC and Al₂O₃ PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Thermal studies have been carried out on a series of particulate (SiC and Al₂O₃) reinforced 6061 Al metal matrix composites. Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis have provided, respectively information on formation or dissolution of precipitate phase(s) and effect of temperature on short-term storage modulus of the materials. Also these studies can be used to identify the phase changes responsible for the maximum damping properties of the materials.

Keywords: Particulate, Composites, DSC, DMA, Precipitates, Stable, Metastable, Equilibrium, Storage & Loss Modulus, Damping properties.

INTRODUCTION:

In recent work reported in the literature, thermal analysis techniques like Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) have been employed to study the change in enthalpy/specific heat, which is considered to be associated with formation/dissolution of the precipitates [1-5] in particulate reinforced metal matrix composites having heat-treatable alloy matrices such as 6061-Aluminium. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) is another thermal analysis technique that can be used to study, in particular, changes in (short term) storage modulus as a function of temperature, as well as providing other information such as damping characteristics [6-10].

As part of a broad research program, the present authors have used DSC and DMA techniques to study microstructural/physical characterisation of a series of PMMC materials, and results obtained so far constitute the subject matter of this report.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials used in this study are as follows:

- 1) 10% V_f(volume fraction) SiC/6061, 2) 20% V_f SiC/6061, 3) 10% V_fAl₂O₃/6061,
- 4) 15% V_fAl₂O₃/6061, 5) 20% V_fAl₂O₃/6061, 6) 20% V_fAl₂O₃(MicroSphere)/6061, (Comral- 85), 7) 6061, unreinforced.

Representative microstructures of composites 1 to 6 are provided in Figures 1 to 6. Details about the materials are given elsewhere [11]. DSC and DMA experiments were conducted with specimens in (a) as-received, and (b) T6 condition i.e. solution treated at 530°C for 1.5 hr, water-quenched to room temperature, 20 hr preaging at room temperature followed by aging at 175°C for 8 hr.

For DSC studies, a Du Pont 910 DSC unit and a Du Pont 2100 Thermal Analyser were

employed with discs of the PMMC materials of 5 mm diameter and 0.5-1.0 mm thickness. The temperature range investigated was 25°-475°C using a scan rate of 20°C/min.

DMA studies were carried out using a Du Pont 983 Dynamic Mechanical Analyser and a Du Pont 2100 Thermal Analyser, and version 6.0 software was used. Specimens in the form of rectangular strips, approx. 30 mm long x 12 mm wide x 1.5 mm thick were clamped between two parallel arms. Specimens were oscillated a constant amplitude (0.3 mm) and a resonant frequency mode was used in the present experiments.

The frequency of oscillation is directly related to the stiffness i.e. storage modulus of the specimen (E') whilst the energy needed to maintain constant oscillation amplitude is a measure of the loss modulus (E'') of the material, the ratio of E''/E' is known as $\tan \delta$ and a measure of the damping of the material.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

DSC: Examples of DSC traces of a 10% $V_fAl_2O_3/6061$ composite, as-received and in T6 condition are shown in Figures 7 & 8. The peaks identified and the corresponding temperatures in the DSC traces for all composites examined are presented in Table 1. The peaks in the Figures 7 & 8 are determined with respect to the base lines (not shown in the figures). As can be seen in Table 1, all materials show a weak exothermic peak, (No.1) at 170°C and a weak endothermic peak, (No.2) at 220°C, possibly due to, respectively, the formation and dissolution of the G.P. zones as observed by Badini et al. [2,4].

The next peak seen in all materials is an exothermic one (No.3) occurring in the temperature range 245°-275°C. It is believed that this peak is due to the formation of metastable, (β'') and stable, (β') precipitates [2]. In all PMMC materials (1 to 6), examined in this study, the β'' and β' transformations in the aging sequence fall at lower temperature as compared to the 6061 matrix alloy (Peaks 3 & 5: 250° & 305°C) and hence the precipitation reactions in composites seem to occur much faster than in the unreinforced alloy.

A large and complex endothermic area appears for all materials followed by the above two exotherms which is believed to be due to dissolution of precipitates [4] and occurs at a temperature around 450°C. Immediately after this, an exothermic peak appeared at relatively high temperature, 480°C for the T6 materials, possibly due to formation of equilibrium precipitates (incoherent β -phase) which is again followed by the endotherm, possibly associated with the dissolution of the equilibrium β precipitates [3] and this temperature is close to the solutionizing temperature (530°C) for the matrix alloys.

DMA: A typical DMA run showing changes in the storage modulus (E'), the loss modulus (E'') and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature is presented in Figure 9. In general, the storage modulus of the composites appears to be dependent on the volume fraction of the reinforcement in the matrix alloy as shown in Figure 10. The absolute values of E' at room temperature for all PMMC materials examined in this work are consistently less (by 18 GPa) than corresponding values reported in the literature for such materials. The 20% V_fSiC composite (Material 2) retains the highest modulus at all temperatures in both conditions whilst the unreinforced alloy showed the lowest modulus.

The temperatures at which a maximum (point of inversion) in $\tan \delta$, Figure 9, is observed for materials 1 to 7 are listed in Table 2. The maxima are considered to relate to a transformation

process in the material and are obtained from the corresponding DSC plots, also noted in Table 2.

CONCLUSION:

From the DSC and DMA studies the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) The formation of equilibrium precipitates β is insensitive to the amount and type of reinforcements (SiC, Al₂O₃) present in the matrix alloy (6061).
- 2) Peak age-hardening behaviour which is due to the formation of coherent precipitates is sensitive to the amount and type of reinforcement.
- 3) 20% SiC/6061 retains the highest storage modulus (E') at all temperatures in both T6 and as-received conditions whereas 6061 has the lowest E'
- 4) From a combined study of DSC and DMA it is possible to identify the phase/phases change responsible for the maximum damping properties of the materials.

Acknowledgements:

The authors wish to thank Dr. Malcolm Couper and Dr. Kenong Xia of Comalco Research Centre, Thomastown, Vic., for providing the materials used in this study. The work was presented at the 3rd Australian Forum on Metal Matrix Composites held at the University of New South Wales, Australia on December 7, 1992.

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Table 1: Analysis of DSC Scans of Reinforced and Unreinforced 6061 Al-Alloys.

Materials	HT Cond.	Temperature in °C of the Peaks							
		Peak 1	Peak 2	Peak 3	Peak 4	Peak 5	Peak 6	Peak 7	Peak 8
6061	ASR	170 (+)	225 (-)	270 (+)	405 (-)	445 (+)	525 (-)		
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	250 (+)	280 (-)	305 (+)	455 (-)	485 (+)	525 (-)
10% SiC	ASR	170 (+)	220 (-)	270 (+)	320 (+)	450 (-)			
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	275 (+)	290 (+)	350 (+)	530 (-)		
20% SiC	ASR	170 (+)	220 (-)	275 (+)	320 (+)	475 (-)	500 (+)	530 (-)	
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	275 (+)	285 (+)	470 (-)	520 (+)		
10% Al ₂ O ₃	ASR (Fig 7)	170 (+)	220 (-)	275 (+)	535 (-)				
	T6 (Fig 8)	170 (+)	225 (-)	245 (+)	260 (-)	280 (+)	450 (-)	485 (+)	520 (-)
15% Al ₂ O ₃	ASR	170 (+)	220 (-)	245 (+)	525 (-)				
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	250 (+)	290 (+)	445 (-)	470 (+)	520 (-)	
20% Al ₂ O ₃	ASR	170 (+)	220 (-)	275 (+)	420 (-)	470 (+)	520 (-)		
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	250 (+)	300 (+)	455 (-)	490 (+)	530 (-)	
Comral-85	ASR	170 (+)	200 (-)	260 (+)	375 (-)	500 (+)			
	T6	170 (+)	220 (-)	245 (+)	295 (+)	455 (-)	490 (+)	535 (-)	

ASR = As-received HT Cond. = Heat treatment condition
T-6 = T6 heat-treated condition
(+): Exothermic (-): Endothermic

Table 2 : Phase changes from DSC plots at the temperatures where maximum of $\tan \delta$ observed in DMA experiment.
 (β' : Stable precipitates, β'' : Metastable precipitates, $\tan \delta = E''/E'$).

Materials	As-received		T6 treated	
	Temp at max of $\tan \delta$ from DMA (°C)	Phase changes at max of $\tan \delta$ from DSC	Temp at max of $\tan \delta$ from DMA (°C)	Phase changes at max of $\tan \delta$ from DSC
6061	335	Dissolution of β'' and β'	370	Dissolution of β'' and β'
10% SiC/6061	325	Formation of β'	330	Formation of β'
20% SiC/6061	320	Formation of β'	285	Formation of β'
10% Al ₂ O ₃ /6061	325	Formation of β'	360	Dissolution of β'
15% Al ₂ O ₃ /6061	340	Dissolution of β'	325	Dissolution of β'
20% Al ₂ O ₃ /6061	335	Dissolution of β'	335 (Not Prominent)	Dissolution of β'
Comral-85	330	Dissolution of β'	330 (Not Prominent)	Dissolution of β'

Fig 1

Optical micrograph of 6061+20% V_f SiC

Fig 2

Optical micrograph of 6061+10% V_f SiC

Fig 3

Optical micrograph of 6061+10% V_f Al₂O₃

Fig 4

Optical micrograph of 6061+15% V_f Al₂O₃

Fig 5

Optical micrograph of 6061+20% V_f Al₂O₃

Fig 6

Optical micrograph of 6061+20% V_f Al₂O₃ (MS) Comral-85.

Fig 7, 8 : DSC thermograms of the 10% $V_f Al_2O_3/6061$ composite in as-received and T6 condition respectively.

Fig 9,10 : E' , E'' and $\tan \delta$ plots as a function of temperature for 20% $V_f SiC/6061$ in as-received condition and temperature dependence of E' for 10% and 20% $V_f SiC/6061$ in comparison to 6061 Al in T6 condition respectively.